

Dirac Equation form $-Et+px$?

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In (1), we argued that spatial and temporal resolutions of \hbar/p and \hbar/E follow from degenerate values of $A=-Et+px$. In particular, t and x absorb the information of E and p through $1/E$ and $1/p$ making $A=0$ or removing all information from A . We argued that even though this degeneracy only appears in $A=-Et+px$ (not in $ctct-xx$ or $-EE+pp = m_0m_0$), $-Et+px$ links (p,E) and space time (x,t) for $m_0, v=0$ at $x=0$ with all constant $-v$ frames. Given the degeneracy points $n\hbar/p$ and $n\hbar/E$, where n is an integer, we suggested in (1) creating a periodic function $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ which represents a kind of probability, i.e. the quantum free particle wavefunction. The use of this periodic function, however, removes the need for t,x in $-Et+px$, leaving only linear E,p which must be linked to m_0 .

In this note, we first argue that $-Et+px$ really represents the idea that there are setsof (p,E) equivalent to $(0, m_0)$ of the rest frame. The fact that one links space-time (x,t) with (E,p) allows one to pull E and p into resolutions of x and t and remove all information from A , i.e $A=0$. The question we ask here is: Can one use $-Et+px$ to create an equation which directly yields $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$? To do so, we first note that it is really the set (p,E) which defines the physical state as x,t may be any value in $-Et+px$, even non-trajectory values. This suggests an equation in (p,E) and maybe m_0 alone and we have already suggested this idea in a previous note. Here, we suggest that $-Et+px$ yields the resolution gradations $\hbar/p, \hbar/E$ key to the function $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ by pulling E and p information into t and x . Normally, x and t would be independent of E,p . To use E,p,m_0 to create an equation yielding $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ we suggest pulling t and x information into E and p , the exact opposite procedure. We do not set $E=1/t$ or $p=1/x$ because E and p are fixed values, but we do replace E and p with space-time derivatives d/dt partial and d/dx partial. As a result, a linear equation linking E,p and m_0 with space-time appearing through derivatives d/dt partial and d/dx partial should be able to yield a solution of $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$.

We note, however, that (E,p,m_0) in a linear equation represents an operator acting on $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$. If one multiplies this operator by itself one should obtain an operator equation yielding $-EE+pp = m_0m_0$ for consistency. If this is to be the case, then there is more happening than just $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$, one has to introduce matrices in exactly the manner shown by Dirac. Dirac, however, started with $-EE+pp = m_0m_0$ and used $E=-id/dt$ partial, $p=-id/dx$ partial without obtaining these from $-Et+px$. He then decided that the a priori goal was to obtain a linear equation in E, p and m_0 . We suggest that a link may be made by using $-Et+px$ as a starting point.

$-Et+px$ and $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$

In (1), we argued that the Lorentz invariant $A=-Et+px$ mixes space and time with E and p which is usually not done. (Note, one may have $v=dx/dt$ in E,p , but one does not usually have x,t unless one uses $v=x/t$.) The reason for $A=-Et+px$ is that the same Lorentz matrix transforms (p,E) and (x,t) because $x=vt$ and $p=mv$ nonrelativistically.

The coupling of (p,E) with space-time and the minus sign form the metric allow one to remove all information in A , i.e make $A=0$ using:

$$x=x_0+n\hbar/p \quad \text{and} \quad t=t_0+n\hbar/E, \quad n=\text{integer} \quad ((1))$$

One may note that x, t may take any value in $-Et+px$, not just trajectory values and x, t should be independent of $-E, p$. If, however, one makes them dependent through ((1)), $A=0$ (using only the resolution pieces of ((1))) and one has degeneracy defining gradations in space and time.

In (1), we suggested that one cannot ignore $-Et+px$ because it shows that $(0, m_0)$ is linked to various (p, E) sets as viewed from different frames moving at different constant v values. This suggests that it is really the link between (p, E) and $(0, m_0)$ that is key physically because x, t can take on any values.

In (1), we suggested that one may create the function $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ to describe the periodicity of ((1)). We ask, however, whether one may obtain this solution directly from $-Et+px$?

Obtaining an Equation Whose Solution is $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$

The degeneracies in ((1)) follow from using $A=-Et+px$, setting $A=0$ and pulling E and p information into t and x . We have also suggested that physically all that one needs is to focus on (E, p) and $(0, m_0)$. In general E, p are constants, but it is $\partial/\partial t$ and $-\partial/\partial x$ which pull these constants out of $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ which contains the notion of the degeneracies in $-Et+px$. In other words, if the degeneracies are accounted for by $\partial/\partial x$ and $\partial/\partial t$ partial then t and x may be removed from $-Et+px$. In this case, space-time is pulled into E and p through $\partial/\partial t$ partial and $-\partial/\partial x$ partial and one may create a linear equation it seems in E, p, m_0 . This linear equation, however, seems to be problematic because it is really:

$$-EE + pp = m_0 m_0 \quad ((2))$$

which linked E, p, m_0 and this is quadratic. Thus, it seems that one must have more than just $\partial/\partial t$ partial and $-\partial/\partial x$ in a linear equation, although we still suggest that $-Et+px$ is the starting point and indicates that one should consider a linear equation with the degeneracies following form $A=0=-Et+p$. We do not assume a priori that $E=\partial/\partial t$ partial and $p = -\partial/\partial x$, but rather deduce this from $-Et+px$. The desire for a linear equation in E, p, m_0 follows from removing t and x from $-E, p$ because $\partial/\partial t$ partial and $-\partial/\partial x$ together with $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ already convey this information.

As a result, the most general linear equation in E, p, m_0 is one of an operator. If this operator is multiplied by itself, it should yield ((2)). This leads to the notion that matrices must exist as well as $-\partial/\partial x$ partial and $\partial/\partial t$ partial.

Dirac has already solved the problem of introducing 4x4 matrices containing off diagonal Pauli matrices (with $+1, -1$) such that a linear equation with matrices and $\partial/\partial t$ partial, $-\partial/\partial x$ partial yields to an operator which when multiplied by itself yields ((2)) with $E \rightarrow \partial/\partial t$ partial and $p \rightarrow -\partial/\partial x$. As a result, this is not repeated here.

What we suggest is that the starting point is $A=-Et+px$ which is of importance because (A) it links all (p,E) sets with $(0,m_0)$ and shows $A=0$ for a set of x points ((1)). This suggests a periodic function $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ which may replace t,x .

Conclusion

In conclusion, we suggest that the notion of free particle quantum mechanics follows from $A=-Et+px$, i.e through the mixing of (p,E) and space-time in the same equation because the same Lorentz transformation applies to (p,E) and (x,t) . With the metric containing -1 , one may pull E information into t and p information into x such that $A=0$. This allows one to create a set of periodic degenerate points: $x=x_0 + n*\hbar/p$, $t=t_0+n*\hbar/E$. This suggests a periodic function $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$. This periodic function, however, replaces the need for x and t in $-Et+px$, and maps $E \rightarrow i\partial/\partial t$ and $p \rightarrow -i\partial/\partial x$. We suggest that one must still consider (p,E) and $(0,m_0)$ because $-Et+px$ essentially shows the link between these sets related to linear p and E .

We suggest seeking a linear equation in E and p with spacetime now pulled into p and E through $i\partial/\partial t$, $-i\partial/\partial x$. This suggests an operator, but the numerical link between E,p,m_0 is: $-EE+pp=m_0m_0$. Thus, the operator multiplied by itself must create $-EE+pp=m_0m_0$. This leads to the idea that it is not enough to have $i\partial/\partial t$, $-i\partial/\partial x$, but that one needs matrices(4x4 matrices as shown by Dirac).

References

1. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Lorentz Invariant Information and $-Et+px$ Leading to Quantum Free Particle $\hbar/p, \hbar/E$ (preprint, zenodo, 2024)